

**ADVANCED METHODS OF ACADEMIC SINGING AND WORKING ON
VOICES IN OPERA PERFORMANCE**

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Abstract: The classification of voices in opera performance was explained.

Keyword: timbre, opera, voice ,soprano, tenor, baritone.

Vocal in the opera genre is a subspecies of vocal art, which differs from other styles of performance in the breadth of its range. Sometimes it is called classical or academic.

The fact is that academic singing is used mainly with classical music, which is an invariable part of operettas, romances and musicals. For example, in pop performance, the singer's voice is supported by equipment, it is processed and amplified, but in academic singing, the performer has to sound for the whole hall only due to his own voice.

This is a whole art in which literally the whole body is involved. Manners of performance are divided into: melodious style, declamatory and coloratura singing. Already based on the name, it can be assumed that recitative includes elements of conversation. It is a symbiosis of speech and song.

The performer reads in a singsong voice, but at the same time, the intonation is preserved: interrogative notes, incentives, exclamations. Usually this manner is used in the intervals between arias, as a transitional element.

A recitative accompanied only by a harpsichord is called "secco" (literally, dry). But the accompaniment of reading by the orchestra is much more powerful and sounds richer.

There are many classifications of operatic voices. However, most often all categories are grouped into 7 types and they are divided by gender and altitude. The female soprano is the highest voice overall. In soprano, as in other types of voices, there is a division into subgroups depending on the timbre, range, color and weight of the voice. Thus stand out:

Subrette (roles of young, flirtatious girls in comedy genres and operettas).

Coloratura soprano.

Spinto-soprano (the color is darker than in the lyric; it has high light notes).

Lyric soprano.

Dramatic soprano.

Mezzo-soprano. Differs in sound volume and saturation. Its subgroups are coloratura, lyric and dramatic.

Contralto. The lowest singing voice. Occurs rarely. Covers all notes of a small octave. Like the previous types, it is divided into coloratura, lyric and dramatic.

Countertenor. Highest male voice.

Tenor. High male singing voice. It is also subdivided into lyrical and dramatic timbre.

Baritone. Medium sounding voice. Such a voice is universal and allows you to perform most of the heroic and love roles in the opera.

Bass. The lowest voice. Has a deep sound. Height is distinguished:

bass cantante (high bass; melodic and melodious sound);

center (good sound in the low range);

bass profundo (low bass; thick, booming voice).

A performance that requires the performer to have excellent technical mastery of high notes. This singing is filled with complex techniques.

The singer's voice in all registers sounds soft and powerful at the same time, the transitions are smooth, which creates the impression of ease of performance. Coloratura is a complex melody, but there are categories for different voices. So lyrical coloratura are written for light voices, and dramatic ones for larger ones. Attribution to one or another category depends on the range of the voice, its color.

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